

THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF

EPOXY-RESIN/METAL-POWDER COMPOSITES

F.F.T. de Araujo and H.M. Rosenberg

The Clarendon Laboratory, University of Oxford,
Oxford OX1 3PU, England

Abstract

The d.c. electrical conductivity of epoxy-resin/metal-powder composites has been measured at room temperature. In heavily-loaded samples containing Cu, Ag, Au, Sn, Pb and bronze, these systems, which normally have a very high resistance, have a memory switching action. For a volume concentration of 55% they switch to a low resistance (about 100 ohms) when a potential of typically 50-100 V is applied across a sample 1 mm thick. This low resistance is retained even when the potential is reduced to zero. The high resistance can be restored by passing a current of the order of 100 mA through the sample. No switching action was observed for volume concentrations below 20%. For small measuring potentials the electrical resistance did not show any sharp decrease at any particular concentration. Such a decrease has been observed in other systems. The results are discussed in the light of current theories.

Introduction

Whilst the electrical properties of a composite system depend on the properties of each component as well as on the microscopic structure, the literature also indicates that there is some dependence on the method of preparation, e.g. vacuum, outgassing treatment, the way the sample is mixed, if sintering has been used or, in the case of epoxy resins, the matrix and its cure schedule.

The results to be discussed show that these properties are also electric-field dependent. They may be placed in two categories, the properties at 'low' and at 'high' measuring potentials. By a 'low' potential we mean one which does not affect the intrinsic properties of the sample. A 'high' potential is one for which non-linear or switching behaviour is observed.

Theory

Two types of structures are commonly observed in a two-phase system consisting of metallic particles dispersed in an insulating medium and a different theoretical approach is required for discussing the electrical conductivity for each.

One structure corresponds to the situation where the conducting particles are isolated from one another with no electrical connection between them. In this case the system is well described by theories such as that developed by Meredith and Tobias (1960) who developed calculations which were initiated by Maxwell (1881) and by Lord Rayleigh (1892). A review article by Meredith and Tobias (1962) gives an outline of the available theories as well as a discussion of some empirical formulae and experimental results. In general these theories assume that the conducting particles are distributed in a regular array and that they will touch each other only at the limit of maximum packing, which for the cubic lattice is at a volume fraction, $V_f = 0.5236$. The Meredith-Tobias formula is not valid at this point (where the sample would show metallic conductivity) but for V_f a little below the limit it predicts a conductivity which is about six times that of the matrix.

The other structure observed is one where the particles are in electrical contact. They short-circuit the resin and form conducting paths so that the sample shows metallic conductivity at filler concentrations which are well below the maximum packing limit. Experimentally such samples show a sharp decrease in electrical resistance by many orders of magnitude at filler concentrations around 15% by volume. (See Gurland (1966), Scher and Zallen (1970), Aharoni (1972), Scarisbrick (1973), Jachym et al (1974), Malliaris and Turner (1971).)

Theories such as those developed by Bueche (1972), Springett (1973) and Grekila and Tien (1965) as well as calculations using percolation theory (Scher and Zallen (1970) and Seager and Pike (1974)) are able to explain the general behaviour of the conductivity as a function of V_f . However, unlike the theories developed for non-touching particles these do not solve the problem in the same sense. The difficulty in calculating the number of conducting paths, the possible interconnections between them, and the contact resistance between the touching particles makes it very difficult to relate the calculations to experimental determinations. Nevertheless, the onset of metallic conduction at relatively low concentrations (around 15%) is explained by these authors.

Experiments and Specimens

In the present experiments the matrix used was an epoxy-resin Epikote 828 (Shell) with Epikure NMA hardener and BDMA accelerator used in the proportions of 100:90:0.5 by weight, respectively. The metallic particles (copper, silver, gold, tin, lead, bronze and stainless steel) were in most cases of spherical shape with mean diameters below 100 micron.

The sample was prepared by first mixing the resin, hardener and accelerator and then the powder was stirred in with it and the mixture was placed in a vacuum oven at 40°C for degassing. The mixture was then transferred to a glass tube of internal diameter ~ 5 mm which had previously been coated with a silicone release agent. This was followed by further degassing. The consistency of the uncured resin allows the metal powder to settle and this is used for the preparation of the heavily-loaded samples. For lower filler concentrations the sample was rotated (3 r.p.m.) during cure in order to obtain a uniform filler distribution. In general samples were prepared with filler concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 55% by volume.

After cure slices about 1 mm thick were cut from the sample and these were used as the experimental specimens. Electrical contacts were made by painting both faces of the slice with a silver-dag dispersion or a silver-filled adhesive. Pressure contacts with silver-plated electrodes were used for connecting the sample into the measuring circuit. In order to measure high values of resistance, using a low potential, a Keithley 610 C electrometer was used. Small values of resistance were measured with a solartron 7040 digital voltmeter which uses a constant current of 100 μ A when operating in the range 0-1000 ohm.

For curing the resin we used two different cure programmes; a precure of 2 hours at 100°C followed by either 4 hours at 200°C or by 16 hours at 125°C.

Results and Discussion

'Low' Potential Measurements

Apart from some exceptions in the case of heavily-loaded samples which we shall discuss later, all other samples showed an electrical resistance that was very similar to that of the unfilled resin. No sharp change was detected and no onset of metallic conductivity was found at any filler concentration up to concentrations $V_f = 0.4$.

A precise value for the resistance of these samples is not given because of the experimental difficulty of measuring such high resistances. (The electrical resistivity of the unfilled resin is of the order of 10^{16} ohm-cm, and it would appear that for the filled sample it is always higher than 10^{14} ohm-cm.) Even though we have not been able to make satisfactory measurements it would appear that a theory such as that of Meredith and Tobias (1960) would describe the situation.

The heavily-loaded samples with filler concentrations around 55% are a special case. They were kept stationary during cure so that the particles settled under gravity and this favoured an electrical contact between them. However, not all samples prepared in this way showed a metallic conductivity and even when they did this conductivity seemed to be sensitive to external factors. For example, a thermal shock was found to destroy the conductivity of a silver-filled sample, and for a reduced copper sample some slices cut from it were non-conducting whilst others were conducting.

Furthermore a dependence on the cure schedule has also been found; e.g. for silver the final state of a low temperature cure sample (16 hours at 125°C) is electrically conducting whilst the high temperature cure sample (4 hours at 200°C) is not. This might be due to the difference in the thermal expansion coefficient of the resin and of the metal. When the temperature is raised the resin which has a higher expansion coefficient than the metal will move the particles apart thereby preventing electrical contact.

'High' Potential Measurements - Switching Effects

The most obvious way to measure a high resistance is to apply a high potential across the sample so that the current through it is increased to a range which is suitable for an accurate comparison between samples. However, this is not always satisfactory. Non-linear current-voltage characteristics have been observed well before the breakdown region (Levinson and Philipp, 1974) and it is very difficult to ensure that non-ohmic effects do not upset the

resistance measurements. In heavily-loaded samples it was certainly not possible to do this and for example in reduced copper specimens, the breakdown voltage was about 100 V for a sample 2 mm thick.

By inserting a 1000 ohm resistance in series with the sample (which controls the current after breakdown) it was observed that this breakdown occurred without any apparent damage to the sample and furthermore the sample remained conducting even after the potential had been removed. If the 1000 ohm resistance was then short-circuited and the current through the conducting sample increased it was found that at a critical current of a few hundred mA the conduction stopped and the sample switched back to an OFF state with a resistance higher than 10^7 ohm.

A typical set of results is shown in figure 1. It shows the voltage required to switch the sample ON and its resistance in the ON state. Between each pair of points the sample was switched OFF by passing a sufficiently high current through it. It will be noted that whilst the first twenty or so cycles give a rather erratic set of points, the specimen then seems to settle down to a more consistent behaviour, although this may be followed by another region of higher scatter.

When the conducting paint on one of the faces of a switched ON sample was removed and a point contact was used as a probe it was found that there was only one very small area on the face where conduction occurred through the specimen. This would suggest that the conducting path is through a filament rather than through the bulk material. This is similar to the observations of Pearson et al (1962) and Ovshinsky (1968) on amorphous semiconducting glasses.

The actual switching mechanism has not yet been identified but there are two possibilities. After breakdown a conducting (metallic?) filament grows either through the oxide coats around two particles in contact, or through the resin layer between two separated particles. Switching in materials such as copper oxide has indeed been observed (Cook, 1970; Silva, Dir and Griffiths, 1970) and seems to be due to metallic filaments and it is believed that other metallic oxides would produce similar behaviour (Gibbons and Beadle, 1964). The possibility of switching by some electronic process within the resin cannot be ruled out although we do not know of any experimental work which might confirm this. The fact that the switching characteristics which have been observed are remarkably similar in reduced and non-reduced copper, silver, lead, tin and gold suggests that the same mechanism is involved in each case and thus the possibility that there is a switching mechanism in the oxide itself does not seem likely.

Switching was observed not only in the heavily-loaded samples but also at filler concentrations higher than 20% by volume. In silver, for example, a 25% sample switched at 200 V whilst a 10%

sample withstood 2 kV without any breakdown. This can be explained in terms of a conducting path as predicted by percolation theory with the additional assumption that particles on the path are slightly separated from one another by a resin or oxide film.

No satisfactory switching was observed in samples containing stainless steel. On trying to switch OFF so much heat was generated that irreversible damage occurred and the sample continued to conduct.

Conclusions

For composites made from an epoxy-resin matrix filled with reduced and non-reduced copper, silver, gold, tin, lead and bronze the following observations have been made.

For 'low' measuring potentials (except for some heavily-loaded samples) no sharp change in the electrical conductivity was observed at any particular concentration.

Due to the high value of the resistance ($\sim 10^{16}$ ohm) a precise measurement could not be made but it is believed that the system may be described by theories such as that of Meredith and Tobias (1960).

When the measuring potential was increased to a few hundred volts it was found that samples with filler concentrations higher than about 20% by volume showed a resistance breakdown. By controlling this breakdown current an ON-OFF switching effect could be produced.

The switching effect is explained in terms of a conducting filament that sustains the conducting state even for zero potential. Breakdown occurs when the current through this filament is increased to a certain value and this gives the OFF state.

The actual material of this conducting filament has not been identified but a metallic filament that grows through a thin layer of insulating resin or oxide seems possible.

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Sample Red. Copper 100 μ m - $V_f = 0.53$ - Diam.=5mm - L=2mm

1. The voltages to switch ON and the resistances in the ON state for consecutive switching cycles. The sample was a heavily-loaded ($V_f = 0.53$) specimen of reduced copper powder in epoxy-resin.